

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory App

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HerStory Consortium

Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Author	Modification
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1	1	15/01/2025	Alicia García-Holgado	Reviewing, adding section 3 and preparing the final version

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1. Introduction

The HerStory Mobile App is an innovative digital tool designed to bring the impactful stories of influential women to life, providing an engaging and interactive experience for users. This app focuses on exploring the historical contributions of women across various European cities, guiding users through carefully selected landmarks and narratives. Through a combination of interactive elements, rich multimedia, and historical insights, the HerStory Mobile App aims to make the history of women's contributions both accessible and educational.

Deliverable 3.4 represents the development of a fully functional mobile application for the HerStory project, a key milestone in the project's progress and a step toward deeper community engagement and awareness. This document outlines the detailed steps taken to develop the app, from initial planning to final launch, ensuring that it offers a seamless and informative experience to all users.

2. Development process and key features of the HerStory mobile app

2.1. Mobile app development process

The following steps outline the development process for transforming an existing platform into a mobile app. This process includes a series of stages that ensure the app's functionality, usability, and performance are optimized for mobile devices while maintaining consistency with the original platform. The steps include planning, app development and adaptation, internal testing and feedback, and ultimately launching the app to the store.

Planning

Since this app was a transformation of an existing platform, the initial step was to assess the platform's existing components—its functionality and content structure. Planning involved identifying what needed to be adapted or optimized for mobile use, ensuring compatibility with Android app development requirements.

App development and adaptation

The platform’s features were converted into app-friendly versions without building the app from scratch. The app was designed to offer a smooth and consistent user experience, mirroring the platform’s main elements in a mobile-friendly format.

Internal testing and feedback

Once the primary functionality was ready, internal testing was conducted to gather feedback from partners who were familiar with the original platform. This helped identify issues or areas for improvement before a broader release.

App launch

The development team ensured that the app complied with Google Play Store guidelines, including security, performance, and design standards. Once it passed these checks, the app was submitted to the store for approval and release.

2.2. Key features of the HerStory mobile app

Feature Name	Purpose	Components
Explore women’s history	To uncover the history of remarkable women who have influenced European cities.	Interactive map-based interface, historical narratives, and locations related to influential women in various fields.
Landmark information	Provide detailed information on significant landmarks associated with these women.	Highlighted landmarks, museums, historical sites.
In-depth profiles	Offer deeper insight into the lives of women who made significant contributions in various domains.	Biographies of scientists, artists, writers, and other pioneers, with detailed contextual information.
Cultural exploration	Enhance cultural understanding by linking the landmarks to broader societal contributions.	Stories about women’s achievements in art, literature, politics, and education.
Multilingual online maps	Provide users with easy access to locations and historical points in different languages.	Maps available in English and local national languages, helping tourists and locals explore key landmarks connected to women's history.
Treasure hunt activity	Offer an engaging, interactive experience to enhance learning and exploration during tours.	Integrated with Actionbound, an app providing a treasure hunt game that can be used as a complementary activity during site visits and tours.

2.3. ActionBound Treasure Hunts

HerStory's mobile app uses interactive treasure hunts to complement online map exploration, allowing users to discover the stories of remarkable women across various cities. To bring this to life, the app uses ActionBound. By engaging with ActionBound's quizzes, participants answer history-related questions and unlock new points on the map, making learning both enjoyable and educational. This interactive format encourages active exploration and enhances the experience of uncovering the significant roles women have played in shaping society in each city.

The ActionBounds for each city are listed below.

Athens, Greece: <https://actionbound.com/bound/herstoryathens>

HerStoryAthens
by csicy

☆☆☆☆☆

ATHENS

Scan this Code with the Actionbound App to start the Bound.

Singleplayer Bound

- 2 information
- 14 quizzes
- 14 locations

Create Bound Challenge

Start guide

Lecco, Italy: <https://actionbound.com/bound/HerStoryLecco>

A HerStoryLecco
by csicy

☆☆☆☆☆

 Create Bound Challenge

 Start guide

Scan this Code with the [Actionbound App](#) to start the Bound.

 Singleplayer Bound

- 15 information
- 15 quizzes
- 15 locations

Fort-de-France, Martinique, France:

<https://actionbound.com/bound/HerStoryMartinique01>

A HerStoryMartinique01
by csicy

☆☆☆☆☆

 Create Bound Challenge

 Start guide

Scan this Code with the [Actionbound App](#) to start the Bound.

 Singleplayer Bound

- 5 information
- 15 quizzes
- 5 locations

Nicosia, Cyprus: <https://actionbound.com/bound/herstorynicosia01>

A HerStoryNicosia01 ★★★★☆
by csicy

NICOSIA

Create Bound Challenge

Start guide

Scan this Code with the [Actionbound App](#) to start the Bound.

Singleplayer Bound

6 quizzes
5 locations

Salamanca, Spain: <https://actionbound.com/bound/HerStorySalamanca01>

A HerStorySalamanca01 ☆☆☆☆☆
by csicy

Salamanca

Create Bound Challenge

Start guide

Scan this Code with the [Actionbound App](#) to start the Bound.

Singleplayer Bound

12 information
11 locations

Sofia, Bulgaria: <https://actionbound.com/bound/herstorysofia01>

A HerStorySofia01
by csicy

Scan this Code with the [Actionbound App](#) to start the Bound.

- Create Bound Challenge
- Start guide
-

 Singleplayer Bound

- 13 information
- 30 quizzes
- 13 locations

Velenje, Slovenia: <https://actionbound.com/bound/herstoryvelenje>

A HerStoryVelenje
by csicy

Scan this Code with the [Actionbound App](#) to start the Bound.

- Create Bound Challenge
- Start guide
-

 Singleplayer Bound

- 1 information
- 9 quizzes
- 9 locations

Vilnius, Lithuania: <https://actionbound.com/bound/herstoryvilnius01>

A HerStoryVilnius01
by csicy

☆☆☆☆☆

🏆 Create Bound Challenge

📄 Start guide

🔍

Scan this Code with the **Actionbound App** to start the Bound.

👤 Singleplayer Bound

- 📄 7 information
- 🔍 6 quizzes
- 📍 6 locations

2.4. Mobile app preview

The mobile application can be found at the following link:

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.csicy.herstoryapp>

HerStory

Center for Social Innovation

1+ Downloads PEGI 3

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About this app

Explore the rich and often overlooked history of remarkable women who have shaped European cities with our innovative map-based app. Whether you're a traveler, history enthusiast, or simply curious, this app allows you to journey through time and discover key locations linked to the lives and achievements of trailblazing women in culture, politics, science, the arts, and more.

From renowned figures like scientists, artists, and activists to lesser-known pioneers, the app highlights their contributions by showcasing significant landmarks, museums, and historical sites across Europe. With each location, you can delve into detailed...

Updated on Sep 25, 2024

Education

Data safety

Safety starts with understanding how developers collect and share your data. Data privacy and security practices may vary based on your use, region, and age. The developer provided this information and may update it over time.

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No data collected
[Learn more](#) about how developers declare collection

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3. HerStory open educational tool for creating treasure hunts

The HerStory open educational tool is an innovative web-based application designed to support urban treasure hunts. The tool was developed in Spanish, as it was a student project coordinated by HerStory Salamanca team.

This tool was not included in the description of the project; **it is an additional result**. However, during the development of the project, the team identified a lack of tools for developing treasure hunts from an educational point of view. By leveraging gamification and digital accessibility, the tool enhances the HerStory project's reach and impact, providing an open educational tool for creating treasure hunts as an educational activity, not only for teachers, but also for youth associations, NGOs, and any kind of stakeholder interested in making a treasure hunt activities in their cities.

The tool was developed by the University of Salamanca as a student project of the Degree in Computer Sciences. The main developer was Christian Domínguez Vicente under the supervision of Alicia García Holgado and Andrea Vázquez Ingelmo (University of Salamanca, Spain).

3.1. Technical overview

The treasure hunt tool was developed using a structured, iterative approach to ensure its functionality and adaptability. Three digital prototypes were created during the development process to refine its features and address technical challenges.

- **Version 1:** The initial prototype offered a basic structure with essential functionalities. It introduced the core concept of an urban treasure hunt platform and included features such as user registration, question management, and route creation.
- **Version 2:** This version enhanced the user interface and added improvements based on feedback from initial tests, such as simplified workflows and better navigation tools.

- **Version 3:** The final version integrated advanced features, including map-based navigation, QR code accessibility, and real-time participant tracking, making it a fully functional and user-friendly tool.

The tool was built using Python with the Django framework, offering a solid and secure foundation for managing server-side operations, such as user accounts, data storage, and game logic. For database operations, SQLite was chosen, providing a lightweight yet efficient solution for storing user data, treasure hunt configurations, and performance analytics. The interface was implemented using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, enabling a responsive and cross-platform design. The integration of Leaflet.js, a leading open-source library for interactive maps, allowed for seamless map-based navigation, while the use of QR code libraries enhanced accessibility by simplifying participant registration.

The development process focused on iterative testing and feedback to ensure that the tool met both technical and user requirements.

3.2. Key Features and functionalities

The HerStory treasure hunt tool is structured to provide both flexibility and ease of use for educators while delivering an engaging experience for participants. The tool's core functionalities are as follows:

- **User-Friendly interface:** The tool features an intuitive interface for both treasure hunt organizers and participants, ensuring accessibility for users with varying technical expertise.
- **Customizable content:** Organizers can create tailored routes, define questions, and incorporate multimedia elements to enhance the treasure hunt experience.
- **QR code access:** Participants can join a treasure hunt simply by scanning a QR code, streamlining the process and removing barriers to entry.
- **Participant tracking and scoring:** Organizers can monitor the progress of participants in real-time, review their scores, and ensure a smooth event flow.

This combination of features ensures that the tool can be effectively used in diverse scenarios, from educational field trips to large-scale public events.

The tool was designed with a focus on simplicity, inclusivity, and accessibility:

- Simplified registration process: The use of QR codes eliminates the need for complex sign-ups, allowing participants to join effortlessly.
- Intuitive navigation: The interface provides clear workflows for creating treasure hunts, accessing routes, and tracking progress.
- Map integration: The integration of maps enhances the participant experience by providing visual guidance throughout the treasure hunt.

3.3. Description of the web app

The HerStory open educational tool is available at <https://gincanas.herstoryproject.eu/>.

Upon accessing the application, there is a screen where users can choose their role. Users must register to use the web application's tools. Teachers are required to create an account to use the platform and gain access to features for creating treasure hunts (referred in the tool as "gincanas") and generating guest accounts for participants. These Guest users will participate in the treasure hunts without needing formal registration. Guest accounts only require credentials provided by the teacher, which are used for answering challenges and calculating scores at the end of the activity.

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When logged in as a teacher, users access the main interface, featuring a sidebar menu with options: "Home," "Create Gincanas," "My Gincanas," "Public Gincanas," "Help," and "Log Out". Depending on the section of the website the teacher is on, the sidebar highlights the active option for easy navigation.

Key Features for teachers:

1. Creating gincanas: Teachers are provided with tools to design treasure hunts by defining stops, challenges, and questions at each point of the route.
2. Generating reports: Teachers can track participant progress, calculate scores, and download final results for analysis.

The design prioritizes usability to simplify the treasure hunt creation process while supporting flexible customization options tailored to specific educational needs.

HerStory Gincanas

Prueba
 Editar Prueba
 Configuración
 Puntuaciones
 Inicio
 Crear Gincana
 Mis Gincanas
 Gincanas Públicas
 Ayuda
 Cerrar Sesión

Buscar Buscar

Parada 1: Calle
 51.51431919276946 - 0.13183593750000003
Pregunta:
 ¿Que ves?
Respuestas:
 Nada - Puntos: 2 - Es Correcta: False
 Algo - Puntos: 4 - Es Correcta: True

Parada 2: Plaza
 51.48854489318077 - 0.09452874145507814
Pregunta:
 ¿Que haces?
Respuestas:
 Nada - Puntos: 2 - Es Correcta: False
 No se - Puntos: 2 - Es Correcta: False
 Algo - Puntos: 4 - Es Correcta: True

Parada 3: Rotonda
 51.5193185179038 - 0.06883621215820314
Pregunta:
 ¿Estos jugando a una Gincana?
Respuestas:
 Si - Puntos: 4 - Es Correcta: True
 No - Puntos: 2 - Es Correcta: False

Añadir Guardar Cambios

Participants, typically students, are Guest users in the system. They receive credentials from the teacher that allow them to access the specific treasure hunt assigned to them. These credentials do not require a formal registration process, minimizing barriers to participation. Participants use the web application to navigate the gincana, interact with questions, and submit answers.

PRUEBA

PARADA 1: CALLE

¿Que ves?

Respuestas	Elige respuesta
Nada	Responder
Algo	Responder